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6G SNS

**AMAZING-6G: Amazing Large-Scale Trials and Pilots for
Verticals in 6G**

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INTRO

This newsletter presents the technology enablers identified by the AMAZING-6G project, based on the needs of the AMAZING-6G use cases. The identified enablers may also be used for other vertical use cases with similar requirements. In order for their integration in the AMAZING-6G trials and pilots, the identified technology enablers are particularly those where there are innovation opportunities and in which the project partners have strong expertise.

The identified technology enablers are grouped into the following four (4) categories:

- Communication enablers, including radio, transport and core network enablers.
- Compute as a Service enablers (CaaS), including the enablers in the compute continuum.
- Application enablers and AI, including network exposure APIs and AI-driven application services.
- IoT and localization enablers, including IoT platforms, IoT devices and localization technologies.

Some of the enablers are further split into multiple sub-enablers with similar but still different technical focuses. Figure below illustrates the scope of the AMAZING-6G technology enablers and their association with WP3 tasks.

In this newsletter we focus on conceptual and brief introduction of the identified technology enablers and their associated AMAZING-6G use cases. Interested readers may refer to [Deliverable 3.1](#) of the project for more details including more detailed analyses of use case association per each (sub-)enabler, high-level general designs and use case (or testbed) specific individual designs.

COMMUNICATION ENABLERS

Communication resource management

The demand for network resource consumption is continuously growing due to the proliferation of IoT devices, user equipment (UE), and other connected endpoints. To address this demand, network management must evolve to become more flexible and resilient, enabling dynamic resource allocation, service scalability, and operational flexibility. This enabler consists of the following sub-enablers, addressing different aspects of communication resource management and applicable for different AMAZING-6G use cases: Zero-touch Network and Service

Management (ZSM), network programmability, automated gNB configuration, network performance monitoring and control, (dynamic) identification and selection of backhauling.

Network slicing

Network slicing in cellular systems is based on the concept of running multiple logical networks on a shared physical infrastructure. Each slice represents a virtualized, end-to-end network instance tailored to a specific service profile or customer requirement—for example, enhanced mobile broadband, massive IoT, or URLLC communications. Slices are isolated from one another in terms of control, data handling, and resource allocation, which allows operators to guarantee differentiated SLAs on the same RAN, Core and Transport infrastructure. The orchestration layer ensures lifecycle management of these slices, from creation to scaling and termination, while enforcing performance and security boundaries between them.

Integrated sensing and communication (ISAC)

The ISAC enabler is a modular platform that integrates radio communication and radar-like sensing within a single radio system. It repurposes standard cellular base-station hardware and waveforms to operate as dual-purpose nodes, delivering high-throughput connectivity while simultaneously estimating range, velocity (Doppler), and angle of surrounding objects. By sharing infrastructure between communication and sensing, it reduces duplication of hardware, simplifies deployment, and enables continuous situational awareness alongside reliable connectivity. While motivated by railway requirements in this project, the design principles are domain-agnostic.

Public-private network integration

This enabler aims to enable public networks to interwork with non-public/private networks to extend coverage, up to the public network coverage, even if with lower performances, but enough to guarantee the minimum required for applications. In general, there are two types of private networks: SNPNs (Standalone Non-Public Networks) are private 5G networks that operate entirely independently of any public network, while PNI-NPNs (Public Network-Integrated NPNs) integrate with existing public mobile networks to provide private communication services. An PNI-NPN can either only use the radio network part of the public network or share both the radio network and core network control plane of the public network, via e.g. network slicing.

Multiple-RAT connectivity

Multi-RAT connectivity aims to ensure network coverage and resilience even in difficult-to-reach areas. The following options (sub-enablers) are considered: B5G sidelink, Wi-Fi integration and NTN integration.

COMPUTE AS A SERVICE (CAAS) ENABLERS

Compute resource management

This is a broad technological enabler that embeds principles of closed-loop resource management, covering three essential phases: (i) intelligent service and resource orchestration in compute continuum (decision-making), (ii) intent-based processing (service requirement analysis and validation of decisions made by orchestrators), and (iii) real-time monitoring. This enabler is in charge of monitoring the NFV infrastructure within compute continuum (edge to cloud), making proactive decisions on compute and service scaling, instantiation, relocation/migration, and termination, based on the decisions made by the orchestration layer, to fulfil the service requirements stated in the intents.

Compute continuum

This enabler includes two sub-enablers: distributed user-edge-cloud compute continuum and multi-party cloud, delivering edge and cloud compute resources in a distributed fashion, thereby creating a pool of compute resources that can be used for deploying and managing vertical services associated with the AMAZING-6G use cases.

Cloud-native service design

By following cloud-native principles like declarative configuration, immutability, microservice granularity, and infrastructure abstraction, this enabler provides the agility needed to adapt quickly to dynamic environments. This is particularly important in areas such as edge computing and 5G network slicing, where services must be provided rapidly, resources allocated efficiently, and recovery automated to maintain performance and reliability.

Creation of Kubernetes clusters on demand

The open-source Kubernetes platform enables the pooling of computing resources (like CPU and memory from multiple servers) into a single, unified resource and then takes care of efficiently scheduling and running application "containers" across those resources, ensuring they are always available and can scale seamlessly with demand. Creating a Kubernetes cluster on-demand allows the network to instantly provision a precisely tailored, isolated compute environment exactly where it's needed.

APPLICATION ENABLERS AND AI

AI-as-a-Service framework

The framework provides the foundation for delivering AI capabilities in a flexible, scalable, and simplified manner via 6G infrastructures, to manage and implement the data-driven intelligence of vertical applications. The framework brings together three core technological enablers: AI-as-a-Service (AIaaS), MLOps platforms, and ML model catalogues. AIaaS exposes the access to AI functionalities delivered via edge and cloud resources, through unified and standard interfaces for on-demand interactions. MLOps platforms are used for continuous integration, deployment, operation, and monitoring of ML pipelines. ML model catalogues provide structured repositories of trained and validated ML models, for specific knowledge domains, exposing their metadata to simplify their reusability in different contexts. The combination of these elements, which can be integrated in advanced service offers from network operators or embedded in private mobile networks, can facilitate the AI adoption in several vertical sectors, reducing development effort, promoting reuse of trained models and knowledge sharing, thus contributing to trustworthiness and sustainability of AI-based solutions.

Digital Twin framework

The Digital Twin Framework is designed to create a dynamic, virtual replica of real-world process flows, enabling operators to train, test, and deploy data-driven decision-making tools that reduce bottlenecks and improve operational efficiency. It consists of both application-level and network-level Digital Twins. Operators can use Digital Twins to experiment with different scenarios, such as testing infrastructure investments (e.g., adding an additional crane), evaluating process improvements (e.g., adjusting gate procedures to mitigate peak-hour congestion), or optimizing operational practices (e.g., routing straddle carriers more efficiently during high-demand periods). Historical data serves as the foundation for this development phase, allowing the Digital Twin to be calibrated, validated, and used as a training ground for predictive models and decision-making algorithms.

OpenAPIs for Network Exposure

Network exposure refers to the secure publication of open and standard interfaces for external consumers to easily access network functionalities, such as quality of service (QoS) guarantees, energy management, or resource allocation, in a programmable manner. This capability enables the possibility to realize innovative AMAZING-6G use cases, where application behavior adapts dynamically to underlying network conditions or constraints. The following four main categories of OpenAPIs are being adopted and extended within the project for different use cases: TM Forum APIs, CAMARA APIs for Quality on Demand, CAMARA APIs for Energy Management and CAMARA APIs for Edge/Cloud Continuum.

IOT AND LOCALIZATION ENABLERS

Advanced Localization and Positioning Systems

Accurate localization is a cornerstone for many 6G use cases, such as autonomous mobility, industrial IoT, and infrastructure monitoring. Since no single technology can meet all accuracy and reliability requirements, this project develops advanced hybrid solutions that combine cellular networks, GNSS/RTK, inertial sensors, and cooperative perception.

IoT Connectivity and Infrastructure

This enabler covers the blocks that ensure seamless interconnection between IoT devices, gateways, and communication infrastructures. It focuses on integrating heterogeneous devices and protocols into a unified ecosystem by leveraging 3GPP (including 5G RedCap) and LPWAN technologies, enabling scalable, energy-efficient, and reliable data exchange. The enabler addresses both the hardware components (sensors, gateways, devices) and the communication technologies that allow them to interoperate, aggregate data, and connect with edge or cloud platforms for further processing.

Data Ingestion and Telemetry

This enabler focuses on the collection, transmission, storage, and processing of data generated within IoT environments. It addresses the telemetry chain: from sensor measurements and streaming protocols to scalable storage systems and advanced data processing pipelines. It also includes monitoring platforms that unify heterogeneous data sources, provide real-time visualization, and detect anomalies to maintain operational awareness. By ensuring continuous observability and timely interpretation of events, Data Ingestion and Telemetry enables effective decision-making, early fault detection, and responsive control in different domains.

IoT Service Platforms and Management

This enabler provides the capabilities required to manage and orchestrate IoT ecosystems at scale, bringing together devices, resources, and services into a platform. It decomposes the functionality of full-stack IoT platforms into modular enablers, such as device orchestration, service and resource lifecycle management, message queue fabrics, and exposure functions. Together, these elements ensure that IoT devices can be securely onboarded, monitored, and controlled; that services can be provisioned and optimized across the cloud–edge continuum; and that data and commands can flow reliably between IoT infrastructures and external applications.

IoT Contextual Awareness Systems

This enabler enhances raw IoT sensing data with additional contextual information to provide deeper situational understanding. It covers the collection and fusion of heterogeneous data sources, ranging from local sensors (e.g., LiDAR, radar, cameras) to external inputs such as maps, environmental conditions, and mobility datasets. Advanced data processing and AI/ML methods are applied to clean and correlate these inputs, turning low-level measurements into actionable insights. The result is a more complete awareness of ongoing conditions, enabling applications to anticipate risks, optimize system behavior, and support safe and efficient operations.

Remote Control and Operation (Actuation)

This enabler provides the mechanisms to control IoT devices, machines, and infrastructures remotely and in real time. It includes different layers of actuation: from manual control via dashboards and Remote Procedure Calls (RPCs), to automated responses triggered by rule engines based on telemetry conditions. The scope covers both human-in-the-loop teleoperation, where operators directly command devices such as cranes or robots, and automated actuation, where edge/cloud platforms issue commands to field devices with guaranteed low latency and reliability. By integrating QoS mechanisms, network slicing, and AI-driven decision support, the enabler ensures that commands are executed securely, predictably, and within strict time constraints.

LIST OF TECH. ENABLERS AND USE CASE ASSOCIATION

Table below shows the list of enablers and applied AMAZING-6G use cases. As mentioned above, for some of the enablers we have further specified multiple sub-enablers.

Technology enablers	Sub-enablers	Applied use cases
Communication enablers		
Communication resource management	Zero-touch network and service management	E1, E3, T4, T5
	Network programmability	T4
	Automated gNB configuration	P1, T4, T5
	Network performance monitoring and control	P1, P2, P4, E1, E3, T1, T2, T4, T5
	Identification and selection of backhauling	P1, T5
Network slicing		H1, H2, P3, E1, E2, E3, T1, T2, T3, T4
Integrated sensing and communication		T3
Public-private network integration		E2, T1, T2, T5
Multiple-RAT connectivity	Sidelink	H1, H2, T3
	Wi-Fi integration	H1, H2, P2, P4, T5

	NTN integration	P2, E2
Compute-as-a-Service enablers		
Compute resource management	Intelligent service and resource orchestration in extreme edge/edge/cloud compute continuum	P1, E1, T1, T2, T4, T5
	Intent-based service and resource management	E1, T4
	Real-time monitoring of compute resources and energy consumption in compute continuum	T1, T2, T4
Compute continuum	Distributed user-edge-cloud compute continuum	H1, H2, E1, E2, T1, T2, T4
	Multi-party cloud	H1, H2, E2
Cloud-native service design		E1, T4
Creation of Kubernetes clusters on demand		P1
Application enablers and AI		
AI-as-a-Service framework	AI-as-a-Service	P1, E1, E3, T2
	ML models catalogue	P1, E1, E3, T5
	MLOps	E1, T5
Digital Twin framework		T1, T2, T5
OpenAPIs for Network Exposure	TM Forum API	P1
	CAMARA APIs for Quality on Demand	H1, H2, P2, P3, P4, E2, T1, T2, T4
	CAMARA APIs for Energy management	P2, P3, P4, T2
	CAMARA APIs for Edge/Cloud	H1, H2, E2, T1, T2, T4
IoT and localization enablers		
Advanced Localization and Positioning Systems	Hybrid Localization (5G + GNSS)	E2
	Cooperative Positioning	T1, T2, T5
	GNSS and RTK Positioning	E2, T1, T2
IoT Connectivity and Infrastructure	IoT Gateways	P1, E3, T1, T2, T5
	5G Redcap IoT	H1, H2
	IoT Sensors and Devices	P1, E3, T1, T5
Data Ingestion and Telemetry	Data Collection from sensors and devices	E1, E3, T3
	Monitoring Platform	P1, E1
IoT Service Platforms and Management	IoT Sensors Orchestration (P1, E1
	- IoT Resource Orchestration	P1, E1
	- IoT Resource Registry	P1, E1
	- IoT Service Registry	
)	
	Service and Resource Lifecycle Manager	P1, E1
Message queue fabric	P1, E1	
IoT Exposure Function	P1, E1, T5	
IoT Contextual Awareness Systems		E3, T4
Remote Control and Operation (Actuation)		P5, E3, T5

List of AMAZING-6G use cases (please refer to deliverable D2.1 of the project for more details)

- H1: Wearable ultrasound patch for cardiac function monitoring
- H2: Event-aware real-time reprogramming of pacemaker through wearable patch
- P1: Ubiquitous B5G/6G communication and slice deployment across operators for PPDR AR/VR assisted control centres
- P2: Mission critical services interoperability with other system
- P3: Emergency private B5G/6G communication on-the-move

- P4: Arctic area search and rescue operation
- P5: Emergency private B5G/6G communication on-the-move
- E1: Renewable energy communities
- E2: Robotized offshore wind turbines blade inspection & maintenance
- E3: Solar energy monitoring control and predictions using B5G/5G communications and edge-cloud
- T1: Protection of vulnerable road users
- T2: Enhancing urban security with UGV monitoring
- T3: Wireless signalling on rail tracks
- T4: Tele-operation as a back-up to autonomous, driving
- T5: Port logistics and transport optimization and safety

PROJECT INFORMATION

For comprehensive information on the project's structure, consortium members, use cases, latest news, and contact details, please refer to the official [project website](#). Additionally, deliverables, scientific publications, and other dissemination and communication materials can be accessed through the designated [section](#) of the website.

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- [Newsletter #1 July 2025](#)
- [Newsletter #2 January 2026](#)